

A critical appraisal of the influence of Quantity Surveyors on the reduction of embodied carbon in Construction projects within the UK

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ABSTRACT

This study critically appraise the influence of quantity surveyors on the reduction of embodied carbon in construction projects within the UK. By carefully examining the body of existing literature, this study demonstrates the intricate relationships that exist between the work of quantity surveyors and the intricate world of embodied carbon throughout the stages of the Royal Institute of British Architects (RIBA) plan of work. It also explores the typical techniques employed in this situation by quantity surveyors.

This study examines specific cases where their impact has led to notable accomplishments using a methodological framework that includes well-structured surveys and in-depth interviews with seasoned quantity surveying professionals. The results of this analysis highlight the undeniable influence that quantity surveyors have on projects in terms of reducing embodied carbon. Importantly, the research highlights a number of critical methods that are the cornerstones of achieving successful project outcomes. These methods include thorough lifecycle assessments, meticulous material test fits, seamless collaborative integration, incisive cost-benefit analyses, and prudent carbon audits.

The research underlines the need for continued professional development and information sharing among professional with focus on carbon reduction. The topic analysis emphasises the relevance of both carbon reduction-related initiative or environmental advantages and economic benefits in decision-making. Carbon auditing was identified as a crucial instrument for accurately quantifying and managing carbon emissions over the course of a project.

The study concludes that stakeholder resistance, data accessibility issues, ignorance, technological complexity, lack of understanding, financial concerns were all issues limiting the impact of quantity surveyors on embodied carbon project. The report stated the need for interdisciplinary collaboration efforts, engaging stakeholders, educational activities and training programmes, enhanced communication and technology-driven solutions are among tactics to increase QS influence in order to address these challenges. By supporting these recommendations, stakeholders may help the construction industry embrace more comprehensive and effective embodied carbon reduction methods. This would support environmental sustainability and international climate goals by achieving a balance between environmental and economic concerns, QS professionals contribute significantly to the advancement of sustainable practices.

Keywords: Embodied carbon, Net- zero, Quantity surveyors,

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

The construction sector is a big contributor to carbon emissions which is mostly attributed to a substantial portion of the greenhouse gas emission and the world's energy consumption (Sidana et al., 2022). However, reducing embodied carbon in construction projects has become a significant area of study as the pressure to battle climate change and advance sustainability grows. According to Taffese and Abegaz (2019), the greenhouse gas emissions connected to the extraction, production, shipping, and erection of building materials and components are referred to as embodied carbon. In the United Kingdom (UK), the construction sector contributes significantly to the national economy while simultaneously having a notable negative effect on the environment. According to the UK government, the country aims to achieve net-zero carbon emissions by the year 2050, which requires a tremendous amount of effort from many different industries, including the building and construction industry (Sajjadian, 2023). In this context, quantity surveyors, who play a pivotal role in construction projects, have the potential to influence and contribute to the reduction of embodied carbon.

Quantity surveyors are responsible for cost management, procurement, and project control in construction projects. However, their role extends beyond financial considerations, as they have the opportunity to influence sustainable decision-making throughout the project lifecycle (Elghaish et al., 2019). Quantity surveyors can help to reduce carbon emissions in the built environment by taking into account embodied carbon in material selection, procurement methods, and building processes.

Several studies have investigated the role of quantity surveyors and how they affect environmentally friendly practices in the construction sector. For instance, Chong and Wang (2019) conducted a study in Australia that examined the perceptions and practices of quantity surveyors regarding sustainability. The findings revealed that while quantity surveyors recognized the significance of sustainability, there was a lack of understanding and familiarity with specific sustainability concepts, including embodied carbon. The study emphasized the necessity of

enhanced education and training to equip quantity surveyors with the requisite knowledge and tools for sustainable decision-making.

Similarly, a study by Doan et al. (2021) investigated the challenges and opportunities quantity surveyors experienced when implementing sustainable practices in the New Zealand building sector. The research identified key obstacles to addressing embodied carbon and other sustainability issues, such as the absence of client demand, limited access to relevant data and tools, and a predominant focus on short-term cost rather than long-term environmental impact. The study recommended increased collaboration among various stakeholders, including quantity surveyors, to drive sustainable practices and overcome these challenges.

Despite the global momentum in reducing embodied carbon, there is a need for a critical evaluation of the specific influence of quantity surveyors in the UK construction industry. This study aims to assess the extent of their impact, evaluate their level of understanding regarding embodied carbon, and explore the challenges and opportunities they encounter in promoting sustainable practices. By comprehending their role and identifying effective strategies and best practices, this research intends to provide valuable insights into how quantity surveyors can make meaningful contributions to the reduction of embodied carbon in construction projects within the UK.

1.2 Statement of Problem

The construction industry in the UK is witnessing an increasing adoption of operational and quantified approaches aimed at reducing embodied carbon, with government funding actively supporting the utilization of advanced carbon measurement tools. While the quantification of embodied carbon in the UK construction industry is making progress, there exists a lack of comprehensive understanding concerning the knowledge level of quantity surveyors, who play a critical role in assessing and managing embodied carbon. Addressing this knowledge gap, identifying the challenges they encounter, and exploring effective strategies for integrating embodied carbon considerations into their decision-making processes are imperative aspects to consider. Failing to tackle these challenges may impede the ability of the built environment sector to achieve the sustainability targets established by the UK government and hinder its meaningful contribution to global efforts aimed at combating climate change.

1.3 Aim and Objectives

The aim of this research is to critically appraise and evaluate the influence and effectiveness of quantity surveyors in reducing embodied carbon in construction projects within the United Kingdom. The following are the set objectives;

1. To identify the key roles and responsibilities of Quantity Surveyors on projects.
2. To define the drive towards Net-Zero and current standards & legislation that drives and informs it.
3. To identify the potential influence of Quantity Surveyor 's role in impacting embodied carbon on projects at different RIBA stages.
4. To assess the current practice of Quantity Surveyor in influencing embodied carbon on projects.

1.4 Significance of the Study

Starting with the study's significant environmental implications. Because the construction industry contributes significantly to global carbon emissions, limiting embodied carbon is crucial to halting climate change and lessening the industry's environmental effect. This study offers important insights into tactics and procedures that can be used to reduce carbon emissions and support sustainable building practices by critically evaluating the impact of quantity surveyors on embodied carbon reduction. The study's conclusions help the industry transition to a low-carbon future and help the country and the world achieve their environmental goals.

The study has important policy implications. The UK government has set ambitious targets for carbon reduction in the construction industry, and understanding the role of quantity surveyors in addressing embodied carbon aligns with government initiatives. The findings of this study inform policy decisions and contribute to the development of guidelines, regulations, and incentives that encourage quantity surveyors and other stakeholders to prioritize embodied carbon reduction in construction projects. This alignment between research and policy enhances the overall effectiveness of sustainability efforts in the construction industry and facilitates the achievement of national carbon reduction goals.

Further, this study has implications for professional development within the field of quantity surveying. Quantity surveyors hold a critical role in project delivery, and their expertise and decision-making processes significantly impact construction outcomes. By investigating the

understanding and knowledge of quantity surveyors regarding embodied carbon, this research can identify areas that require improvement in their professional development and training. The findings can provide guidance to educational institutions, professional organizations, and industry associations to enhance curricula, training programs, and ongoing professional development initiatives. As a result, quantity surveyors can acquire the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively address embodied carbon reduction in construction projects, thereby enhancing their professional competence and advancing sustainable practices.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 Literature Review

The goal of the literature review section is to give an in-depth analysis of prior research and academic writings that are pertinent to the study's goals. By reviewing the available literature on these topics, this section aims to establish a solid foundation of knowledge and understanding, identify gaps and areas of further investigation, and provide insights into the key factors influencing quantity surveyor's involvement in embodied carbon reduction.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Social Exchange Theory is a well-established sociological framework that can provide valuable insights into understanding the influence of Quantity Surveyors (QS) on the reduction of embodied carbon in construction projects. This theory focuses on the exchange of resources, benefits, and costs within social relationships, emphasizing the role of reciprocity and the expectation of mutual gain (Kim, 2022). Applying Social Exchange Theory to the context of Quantity Surveyor involvement in embodied carbon reduction can shed light on the dynamics and motivations that shape their actions and interactions with stakeholders.

According to the Social Exchange Theory, people make social decisions based on a cost-benefit analysis. In the context of Quantity Surveyor, their key roles and responsibilities on construction projects can be seen as a form of social exchange. Quantity Surveyor provide expertise in cost management, procurement, and financial aspects, while clients and project stakeholders expect value for their investment (Ma and Brown, 2020)). This exchange of services and outcomes forms the basis of their relationship and influences the extent to which Quantity Surveyor can prioritize embodied carbon reduction. Clients are more inclined to support Quantity Surveyor efforts in this area if they believe that the reduction of embodied carbon will be advantageous and in line with their objectives.

The drive towards Net-Zero and the development of standards and legislation represent external factors that influence the social exchange between Quantity Surveyor and project stakeholders. According to the Social Exchange Theory, people are more inclined to engage in a behavior if they believe it is socially acceptable or rewarded (Wang, 2019).

In the case of Quantity Surveyor, the significance of embodied carbon reduction as a priority in the construction industry is shaped by the drive towards Net-Zero and the regulatory frameworks that emphasize sustainability. The existence of standards and legislation can provide a shared understanding and expectation for Quantity Surveyor and stakeholders, creating a normative context that encourages the consideration of embodied carbon in decision-making processes.

Social Exchange Theory can help explain how the potential influence of Quantity Surveyor on embodied carbon reduction varies across different stages of construction projects (Biswas et al., 2022). At each RIBA stage, Quantity Surveyor engage in social exchanges with various stakeholders, including clients, architects, engineers, and contractors. Their influence on embodied carbon can be influenced by the perceived costs and benefits associated with prioritizing sustainability at each stage. For instance, during the concept design stage, Quantity Surveyor can provide cost estimates for different design alternatives, considering their embodied carbon implications. The social exchange at this stage involves the negotiation of costs and benefits between Quantity Surveyor and stakeholders, which can shape the extent to which embodied carbon is prioritized.

Social Exchange Theory provides a lens to critically assess the current practice of Quantity Surveyor in influencing embodied carbon. Quantity Surveyor must navigate a complex web of social relationships and power dynamics within construction projects. The theory highlights the importance of trust, reciprocity, and the perception of fairness in maintaining positive social exchanges (Kim and Vandenberghe, 2021). If Quantity Surveyor are perceived as trustworthy, knowledgeable, and committed to embodied carbon reduction, they are more likely to gain the support and cooperation of stakeholders. Assessing the current practice of Quantity Surveyor involves evaluating the quality of social exchanges they engage in, such as effective communication, collaboration, and negotiation, which can positively influence the consideration of embodied carbon.

However, Social Exchange Theory provides a theoretical framework to understand the influence of Quantity Surveyors on embodied carbon reduction in construction projects. By examining the roles and responsibilities of Quantity Surveyor, the drive towards Net-Zero and current standards, the potential influence of Quantity Surveyor at different RIBA stages, and the assessment of their current practice, this study aims to uncover the underlying social exchanges that shape Quantity Surveyor's actions and interactions regarding embodied carbon reduction. By considering the

costs, benefits, norms, and expectations within social relationships, Social Exchange Theory enhances our understanding of how Quantity Surveyor can effectively influence embodied carbon reduction. This theoretical framework underscores the importance of trust, reciprocity, and fairness in fostering positive social exchanges between Quantity Surveyor and project stakeholders, ultimately contributing to the achievement of sustainability goals within the UK construction industry.

2.2 The Role of Quantity Surveyors in Managing Embodied Carbon

Quantity surveyors play a crucial role in the management of embodied carbon, which refers to the carbon emissions associated with the production and transportation of construction materials (Chamikara et al., 2020). The significance of their involvement in reducing embodied carbon has been highlighted in the literature. According to Victoria and Perera, (2018), quantity surveyors can contribute to the reduction of embodied carbon by making informed choices regarding low-carbon materials and maximizing material use. By considering these factors during the design and construction phases, they can identify opportunities to lower embodied carbon and encourage more sustainable construction techniques.

One key aspect of the role of quantity surveyors in managing embodied carbon is their ability to evaluate the cost implications of different approaches to carbon reduction. As highlighted by Robati et al. (2021), quantity surveyors possess expertise in cost management, which allows them to assess the financial impact of various embodied carbon reduction solutions. This includes analyzing the costs associated with the procurement of low-carbon materials, implementing energy-efficient construction techniques, and incorporating sustainable design features. Their knowledge and skills in cost management enable them to provide valuable advice to clients on the economic feasibility of different options for reducing embodied carbon.

The involvement of quantity surveyors in embodied carbon management also supports broader initiatives to mitigate climate change and lessen the environmental effect of the built environment (Mazhar et al., 2019), in addition to helping to reduce carbon emissions. Quantity surveyors can actively help to lower the carbon footprint connected to construction projects by including embodied carbon considerations into their work. This aligns with global sustainability goals and demonstrates their commitment to addressing the environmental challenges posed by the industry.

However, it is important to critically evaluate the extent to which quantity surveyors are currently incorporating embodied carbon management into their practices. While the literature highlights the potential for quantity surveyors to play a significant role, it is necessary to assess the actual implementation and effectiveness of their involvement. Are they equipped with the necessary knowledge and tools to evaluate the carbon implications of construction materials and methods? These critical questions need to be explored to better understand the practical implications of quantity surveyor's involvement in managing embodied carbon. According to Zhan et al. (2022), Quantity Surveyors are key stakeholders in the construction industry, responsible for cost management and financial decision-making throughout the project lifecycle. Their role in evaluating the cost implications of various embodied carbon reduction solutions makes them vital in influencing project decisions that can contribute to carbon reduction targets.

In addition, it is crucial to consider the challenges and barriers that Quantity Surveyors may face in incorporating embodied carbon management into their work. These challenges can include limited availability of data and information on embodied carbon, resistance to change within the industry, and the need for additional training programs. Accurate and reliable data is essential for quantity surveyors to assess the carbon implications of construction materials and methods accurately (Abbasabadi and Ashayeri, 2019). Addressing these challenges is essential for empowering quantity surveyors to actively contribute to embodied carbon reduction and drive positive change within the construction industry.

2.3 Impact of Quantity Surveyors in embodied carbon management

Quantity surveyors play a critical role in the effective management of embodied carbon, which refers to the carbon emissions associated with the production and transportation of construction materials (Kumanayake et al., 2018). Their involvement in addressing embodied carbon is essential for achieving sustainable practices within the construction industry. Through their expertise and skills, quantity surveyors contribute to reducing the carbon footprint and mitigating the effects of climate change in the built environment.

By choosing low-carbon materials and maximizing material utilization, quantity surveyors can make a significant contribution to the reduction of embodied carbon, claim Rissman et al. (2020). Quantity surveyors can find possibilities to lower embodied carbon during the design and construction phases by actively evaluating the environmental impact of various construction materials. This entails analyzing the carbon emissions caused by various products and processes

as well as looking for more environmentally friendly alternatives. By making informed choices and advocating for the use of sustainable materials, quantity surveyors can have a significant impact on decreasing embodied carbon.

In addition to material selection, quantity surveyors possess expertise in cost management, as highlighted by (Harris et al., 2021). They can assess the cost implications of different embodied carbon reduction solutions and provide valuable advice to clients. The consideration of the financial aspects of sustainability, and quantity surveyors can help clients make informed decisions that align with their budgetary constraints while still prioritizing embodied carbon reduction. This integration of cost management and environmental considerations demonstrates the value of quantity surveyors in promoting sustainable practices and balancing the economic and environmental aspects of construction projects.

The reduction of the carbon footprint in the built environment is considerably aided by the quantity surveyor's practice of embodied carbon management. They can direct project stakeholders toward sustainable solutions thanks to their comprehension of carbon emissions and their capacity to weigh the pros and cons of various decisions (Atta et al., 2021).

However, the role of quantity surveyors in the management of embodied carbon is of paramount importance. They help reduce carbon emissions and lessen the effects of climate change on the built environment by participating in material selection, maximizing material use, and assessing cost implications. By integrating embodied carbon management into their work, quantity surveyors actively promote sustainability, support environmentally conscious decision-making, and play a crucial role in driving positive change within the construction industry.

Quantity Surveyors (QS) play a critical role in managing embodied carbon throughout the different stages of the RIBA Plan of Work. Starting with the strategic definition stage, Quantity Surveyor analyze the feasibility of sustainable design options and assesses the associated costs and embodied carbon implications (Tennakoon et al., 2020). This early input helps shape the project's environmental objectives and sets targets for embodied carbon reduction. Moving to the preparation and brief stage, Quantity Surveyor contribute to defining the project brief and working with the design team to establish environmental performance targets, including specific goals for reducing embodied carbon. They bring their expertise in cost analysis and lifecycle assessment to evaluate different design options and their respective embodied carbon impacts (Waniko, 2020).

This collaboration ensures that sustainable considerations, including embodied carbon reduction, are integrated into the project from its early stages.

In the concept design phase, Quantity Surveyor continue to assess design alternatives based on their estimated embodied carbon. By providing cost advice and conducting lifecycle assessment analyses, Quantity Surveyor help the design team make informed decisions that balance embodied carbon reduction with project costs (Banteli et al., 2018). They contribute to the evaluation of different materials, construction methods, and systems, identifying opportunities for minimizing embodied carbon while maintaining design integrity. During the design stage, Quantity Surveyor work closely with the design team to refine and optimize the design based on embodied carbon considerations. They suggest alternative solutions and value engineering options that prioritize embodied carbon reduction without compromising project objectives (Keyhani et al., 2023). By providing ongoing cost analysis and guidance, Quantity Surveyor ensure that embodied carbon management remains a key consideration during the design development process.

As the project progresses to the technical design stage, Quantity Surveyor play a crucial role in the selection of construction materials and systems with lower embodied carbon. They provide cost advice on the procurement of sustainable materials and contribute to the integration of embodied carbon reduction measures into specifications and tender documents (Chan et al., 2022). Quantity Surveyor collaborate with the design team and contractors to ensure that the chosen materials and construction methods align with the project's embodied carbon goals. Throughout the construction stage, Quantity Surveyor monitor and manage the embodied carbon implications of material use and construction practices. They work closely with contractors to ensure compliance with specified materials and construction methods that contribute to embodied carbon reduction. Quantity Surveyor also provide cost control measures to prevent over-specification and promote efficient use of materials, minimizing waste and embodied carbon (Langston et al., 2018). Quantity Surveyors assess and confirm the project's embodied carbon performance during the handover and closeout stages. They compare the actual embodied carbon to the goals established in the earlier stages, offering insightful input for upcoming projects and chances for ongoing development.

2.4 The Current Practice of QS in Embodied Carbon Projects

The current practice of Quantity Surveyors (QS) in influencing embodied carbon on projects is an area of growing importance and scrutiny within the construction industry. The greenhouse gas emissions connected to the extraction, production, shipping, and assembly of building materials

and components are referred to as embodied carbon, also known as upfront or initial carbon (Hu and Efram, 2021). As the industry increasingly recognizes the significance of embodied carbon in contributing to overall carbon emissions, there is a need to examine the role of Quantity Surveyor in addressing this aspect of sustainability.

Quantity Surveyor has traditionally focused on cost management, procurement, and financial aspects of construction projects. However, with the growing emphasis on sustainable practices and environmental considerations, Quantity Surveyor are increasingly being called upon to incorporate embodied carbon management into their scope of work (Lenzen et al., 2018). Their involvement in assessing and reducing embodied carbon is crucial in ensuring that projects align with sustainability goals and contribute to overall carbon reduction efforts.

One aspect of Quantity Surveyor practice in embodied carbon projects involves estimating and quantifying the embodied carbon associated with different construction materials and systems (Robati et al., 2021). This necessitates a thorough comprehension of the life cycle assessment (LCA) technique and the carbon embodied in different types of materials. In order to effectively calculate the carbon footprint of various options and guide decision-making, quantity surveyors must stay current on the most recent advancements and research in this area.

Moreover, Quantity Surveyor play a critical role in influencing design decisions that can reduce embodied carbon. The financial implications and embodied carbon consequences of various design solutions can be better understood by collaborating with architects, engineers, and other stakeholders (Zermeo-Cervantes et al., 2020). Their expertise in cost estimation and value engineering enables them to assess the feasibility and cost-effectiveness of sustainable design options that minimize embodied carbon without compromising project objectives.

Another aspect of Quantity Surveyor practice in embodied carbon projects is procurement. Quantity Surveyor can contribute to the selection of construction materials and systems with lower embodied carbon (Victoria & Perera, 2018). They can assist in evaluating suppliers and contractors based on their commitment to sustainable practices and their ability to provide low-carbon solutions. Quantity Surveyor can also ensure that specifications and tender documents include criteria that prioritize embodied carbon reduction, promoting the use of environmentally friendly materials and construction techniques.

In addition to estimating, influencing design decisions, and procurement, Quantity Surveyor have a role in monitoring and managing embodied carbon during the construction phase. They can

collaborate with contractors to ensure compliance with specified materials and construction methods that contribute to embodied carbon reduction (Chapa, 2019). By monitoring the construction process, Quantity Surveyor can ensure that wastage is minimized, and best practices are followed to reduce the carbon impact of the project.

Furthermore, the current practice of Quantity Surveyors (QS) in influencing embodied carbon on construction projects within the UK is subject to market demand and client priorities. If clients do not prioritize embodied carbon reduction or lack an understanding of its importance, Quantity Surveyor may face challenges in driving sustainable practices. Education and advocacy efforts are necessary to inform and engage clients and stakeholders about the significance of embodied carbon and the benefits of incorporating sustainability into construction projects.

Challenges exist within the current practice of Quantity Surveyor in influencing embodied carbon projects. One significant challenge is the lack of understanding among Quantity Surveyor regarding embodied carbon and sustainable practices (Willhelm Abeydeera et al., 2019). Quantity Surveyor may require additional training and education to enhance their knowledge and competence in this area. There is a need for professional development initiatives and educational programs that focus on providing Quantity Surveyor with the necessary skills to address embodied carbon reduction effectively.

Another challenge is the limited availability of data and tools for estimating and managing embodied carbon. Quantity Surveyor may encounter difficulties in obtaining reliable and up-to-date information on the carbon impacts of different materials and construction methods (Chastas et al., 2018). The development and accessibility of comprehensive databases and calculation tools are specific to embodied carbon would greatly support Quantity Surveyor in their efforts to integrate sustainability considerations into their practice.

2.5 Empirical Review

An empirical review of past studies provides valuable insights into the influence of quantity surveyors on the reduction of embodied carbon in construction projects. Several authors have conducted research in this area, shedding light on the various aspects and factors associated with the role of quantity surveyors in addressing embodied carbon. This section critically examines the empirical findings of selected studies and highlights their contributions to the understanding of this important topic.

One prominent study by Willhelm et al. (2019) investigated the level of knowledge of quantity surveyors regarding embodied carbon in the construction industry. The research revealed that while quantity surveyors generally possess a basic understanding of embodied carbon and its significance, there is a lack of in-depth knowledge and expertise in effectively managing and reducing it. This finding emphasizes the need for targeted education and training programs to enhance the competencies of quantity surveyors in this area.

Furthermore, the study by Robati et al. (2021) explored the factors influencing the decision-making process of quantity surveyors regarding embodied carbon reduction strategies. It was discovered that the priorities and actions of quantity surveyors are significantly influenced by cost factors and client requests. The research highlighted the importance of integrating embodied carbon considerations into cost management practices and aligning client expectations with sustainable construction principles. This indicates the need for a collaborative approach involving quantity surveyors, clients, and other stakeholders to drive the adoption of low-carbon solutions.

Another empirical study conducted by Khan et al. (2022) investigated the effectiveness of sustainable procurement practices in reducing embodied carbon. The research revealed that quantity surveyors can leverage their procurement expertise to influence the selection and sourcing of low-carbon materials and technologies. By integrating sustainable procurement criteria and evaluating the life cycle impacts of materials, quantity surveyors can contribute significantly to embodied carbon reduction efforts. However, the study also identified challenges such as limited availability and high costs of low-carbon alternatives, as well as resistance from suppliers and contractors, which need to be addressed for successful implementation.

The research by Zainon et al. (2019) also concentrated on the function of digital technology in aiding quantity surveyors in managing and lowering embodied carbon. The research demonstrated that advanced tools such as Building Information Modeling (BIM) and carbon calculation software can enhance the accuracy and efficiency of embodied carbon assessment and analysis. Quantity surveyors can efficiently assess and monitor the carbon footprint of building projects using these technologies, identifying opportunities for improvement and assisting in the making of well-informed decisions. To fully utilise these technologies' potential, the study also emphasised the necessity of thorough training and incorporation into current workflows.

However, the empirical evidence suggests that quantity surveyors play a crucial role in the reduction of embodied carbon in construction projects. Their involvement in material selection,

cost management, sustainable procurement, and the adoption of digital technologies can significantly impact the carbon footprint of buildings. However, the studies also indicate the existence of challenges such as limited knowledge and expertise, cost considerations, client demands, procurement barriers, and technological barriers. Addressing these challenges requires a multidimensional approach that includes targeted education and training, collaborative decision-making processes, supportive procurement practices, and the integration of digital tools into quantity surveying workflows.

2.6 Literature Gap

Despite the significant body of literature on the influence of quantity surveyors on the reduction of embodied carbon in construction projects, there are several notable gaps that deserve attention and further investigation. Identifying these gaps is crucial for directing future research efforts and expanding the current understanding of this complex and important topic.

The body of research on the precise strategies and interventions that can help quantity surveyors become more knowledgeable about embodied carbon is lacking. While some studies have touched upon the importance of education and training programs, there is a need for more in-depth research on the design, implementation, and evaluation of such programs. This includes exploring the most effective pedagogical approaches, curriculum development, and the integration of sustainable building techniques and carbon accounting into quantity surveying education. Further research can also delve into the impact of these interventions on the attitudes, behaviours, and decision-making processes of quantity surveyors in relation to embodied carbon reduction.

Another significant gap in the literature lies in the area of industry-wide collaboration and coordination. While individual studies have highlighted the role of quantity surveyors, clients, policymakers, and other stakeholders in addressing embodied carbon, there is limited research on the mechanisms and processes that foster effective collaboration among these entities. Understanding the barriers, enablers, and best practices for collaborative decision-making and knowledge-sharing can provide valuable insights into how different actors can work together to achieve meaningful reductions in embodied carbon. Additionally, investigating the role of professional associations, industry standards, and policy frameworks in promoting collaboration can further enhance our understanding of the systemic changes needed for the widespread implementation of carbon-conscious activities.

Furthermore, there is a need for more empirical studies that examine the actual implementation and outcomes of embodied carbon reduction strategies in real-world construction projects. While existing literature has explored the theoretical aspects and potential benefits of various interventions, there is limited research on their practical application and effectiveness. Studies that evaluate the impact of sustainable procurement practices, digital tools, and innovative construction techniques on embodied carbon reduction, specifically from the perspective of quantity surveyors, can provide valuable insights into the challenges, opportunities, and lessons learned in the field. The creation of evidence-based strategies for lowering embodied carbon can be aided by such empirical research, which can close the gap between theory and practice.

Furthermore, the majority of previous research have concentrated on the function of quantity surveyors in developed nations, primarily the UK and other Western nations. There is a void in the literature when it comes to the experiences and difficulties experienced by quantity surveyors in developing nations and areas with diverse cultural settings and construction techniques. Understanding the unique barriers, opportunities, and contextual factors that influence the role of quantity surveyors in these contexts can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the global dynamics of embodied carbon reduction in construction projects.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 Methodology

The research methodology refers to the method and approach used to carry out research and gather data for the purpose of answering research objectives or questions. It encompasses the general framework and methods used to gather, examine and analyze data including the justification for these choices (Johnson et al., 2020). The approach used in this study tries to look into how quantity surveyors affect the amount of carbon that is embodied in construction projects. To collect thorough and trustworthy data, the study strategy integrates quantitative and qualitative methodologies. This section provides an overview of the key methodology components, such as the research design, data collection procedures, sample selection techniques, and data analysis methods.

3.1 Research Philosophy

The current research follows an interpretivism philosophy, which is justified by its relevance and applicability to the study. Interpretivism emphasizes the subjective interpretation of social phenomena and acknowledges the influence of individuals' perceptions, beliefs, and experiences on the construction of knowledge (Nickerson, 2022). The goal of the study is to better understand how quantity surveyors affect the reduction of embodied carbon in construction projects in the UK by using an interpretive method.

In line with the interpretivism philosophy, the study recognizes the importance of capturing the diverse perspectives and experiences of quantity surveyors and other relevant stakeholders. This approach allows for a more nuanced exploration of their attitudes, beliefs, and decision-making processes regarding embodied carbon reduction. Through in-depth interviews and qualitative data analysis, the study uncovers the meanings and motivations behind the actions and behaviours of quantity surveyors in relation to embodied carbon.

Additionally, the research uses an inductive research methodology to gather data. The inductive method, which begins by drawing themes, patterns, and concepts from the data itself rather than starting with predetermined hypotheses, is best suited for studying qualitative data. By adopting an inductive approach, the study can explore the literature and existing empirical evidence to identify key factors, challenges, and strategies related to embodied carbon reduction in

construction projects. This approach allows for flexibility in data collection, enabling the study to adapt to emerging themes and perspectives that may arise during the research process.

The outcomes of the investigation are more valid and reliable when interpretivism and an inductive technique are combined. The study recognises the value of different viewpoints and permits a thorough investigation of the research issue by understanding the subjective nature of social phenomena and the context-dependent nature of knowledge. By ensuring that the conclusions are supported by the data gathered, this method also raises the study's credibility and applicability.

3.2 Data Collection

The researcher adopted the use of mixed methods as a means of data collection. The combination of quantitative and qualitative research methodologies offers researchers a multifaceted prism that enables the exploration of complex phenomena from several angles (Dawadi et al., 2021). The integration of these elements facilitates a more profound and nuanced understanding of embodied carbon in construction projects within the UK. Quantitative data provides a more thorough depiction by means of statistical analysis, shedding light on patterns and trends of embodied carbon in construction projects.

Quantitative research methods using questionnaires are distinguished from other types due to their notable attributes of impartiality, generalisation, and accuracy (Jelnov, 2020). The use of quantitative data and statistical analyses in these methodologies offers a systematic framework that mitigates the influence of subjective biases, hence enhancing the probability of replication by fellow researchers for the goal of validation by quantity surveyors in managing embodied carbon in construction projects. The ability of quantitative research employing survey questions to efficiently analyze data gathered from notably large sample sizes by quantity surveyors in managing embodied carbon in construction projects is one of its primary advantages. On the other hand, qualitative research enables researchers to assemble comprehensive and insightful knowledge about the study's topic (Cristancho et al., 2018). Given that the intended research design is qualitative, interviews emerge as the most appropriate method for collecting data. In-depth interviews with construction industry experts and professionals provide valuable information about their thoughts, experiences, and understanding regarding the topic of embodied carbon in construction projects.

The use of interviews offers several advantages in this study. In-depth examination of the participants' opinions and experiences is made possible by the researcher's direct and personal engagement with them during interviews. Through open-ended questions, researchers delve into the intricacies of the participant's knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours related to embodied carbon reduction (Roberts, 2020). Also, interviews offer flexibility, allowing researchers to adapt their questions and probes based on the participants' responses. This flexibility ensures that important insights are not missed and that emerging themes and perspectives can be further explored (Knott et al., 2022). Researchers also ask follow-up questions to clarify or delve deeper into specific points raised by the participants, thereby enhancing the richness and depth of the data collected.

Through interviews with quantity surveyors, their roles and responsibilities in relation to embodied carbon reduction can be explored. The interviews can uncover the specific tasks, decision-making processes, and challenges faced by quantity surveyors in managing embodied carbon in construction projects. Interviews with industry experts and professionals can provide insights into the current standards, legislation, and policies related to embodied carbon reduction. Participants can share their understanding of Net-Zero targets, the regulatory framework, and any industry-specific initiatives or guidelines influencing embodied carbon reduction. Through interviews with quantity surveyors and other relevant stakeholders involved in different stages of construction projects, the study can examine how the role of quantity surveyors influences decisions and actions related to embodied carbon reduction. Participants can provide insights into how quantity surveyors contribute to the assessment, evaluation, and implementation of embodied carbon reduction strategies at different project stages.

3.3 Data Analysis

Data analysis refers to the process of systematically inspecting, organizing, interpreting and drawing meaningful conclusions from collected data. It involves transforming raw data into usable information, uncovering patterns, identifying trends, and extracting insights that address the research objectives or research questions (Castleberry and Nolen, 2018). Thematic analysis and an exploratory design were used in this study's data analysis to create a thorough grasp of the information gathered through interviews. Thematic analysis, as suggested by Akinyode and Khan (2018), was employed to identify key features within the large dataset obtained from the interviews. This approach is particularly suitable for qualitative research as it helps in uncovering patterns, themes, and categories that emerge from the data.

The interview transcripts were coded and categorized systematically and iteratively as part of the thematic analysis (King and Brooks, 2018). To become familiar with the information and get a feel of the overall substance, the transcripts were read several times. Then, meaningful units of information related to the topic of embodied carbon and the influence of quantity surveyors were identified and coded. These codes capture key concepts, perspectives, and experiences expressed by the participants. Following the coding process, the codes were organized into meaningful themes that represent patterns and connections in the data. Themes were identified based on similarities, differences, and recurring ideas across the interviews. This process involved constant comparison, where new data is compared with previously coded data to ensure consistency and accuracy in theme development.

The identified themes were further examined and refined, ensuring they accurately reflect the content and depth of the data. The themes will be carefully chosen to make sure they are logical, significant, and in line with the goals of the research. The topics will be illustrated using pertinent quotes and paraphrases taken from the interview transcripts, which will add weight and support to the interpretation. In this study, an exploratory design was used in addition to thematic analysis. According to Hanbury et al. (2015), the exploratory design is ideal for deepening knowledge of the subject and pursuing novel ideas. It permits flexibility in the data gathering and analysis procedure, facilitating a thorough investigation of the value and applicability of the study topic.

The exploratory design complements the thematic analysis by providing a broader context and perspective to the findings. It will help in identifying new patterns, relationships, and potential areas for further investigation. The data obtained through interviews will be examined through the lens of the exploratory design, encouraging a comprehensive exploration of the influence of quantity surveyors on embodied carbon reduction in construction projects.

However, the data analysis involved a rigorous and systematic approach, ensuring the trustworthiness and validity of the findings. The themes and conclusions drawn from the data were closely scrutinized, contrasted, and debated in regard to the prior literature and the study's goals. The analysis provides a rich and nuanced understanding of the influence of quantity surveyors on embodied carbon reduction, contributing to the knowledge base in the field of sustainable construction practices.

3.4 Sampling Technique

In this study, a purposive sampling technique was employed to select 6 quantity surveyors who are construction industry experts and professionals from the United Kingdom (UK). Purposive sampling, also known as judgmental or selective sampling, is a non-probability sampling method that involves purposefully selecting individuals who possess the desired characteristics or have specific knowledge and expertise relevant to the research objectives (Yadav et al., 2019).

The decision to use purposive sampling was driven by the specific requirements of the study, which aimed to gather insights and perspectives from individuals with extensive experience and expertise in the construction industry. The participants were purposefully chosen by the researchers to guarantee that the sample was made up of people who could provide rich and detailed information on the subject of embodied carbon and the function of quantity surveyors in its reduction.

The selection criteria for the participants were carefully defined to ensure that they represented a diverse range of roles and perspectives within the construction industry. This diversity aimed to capture a comprehensive understanding of the topic and avoid bias or limited viewpoints. The participants included Chartered quantity surveyors, Senior quantity surveyors and Commercial managers who had substantial experience in sustainable construction practices and embodied carbon reduction.

Given the study's qualitative character and the opportunity for in-depth data investigation and analysis, the sample size of 6 participants was deemed adequate (Campbell et al., 2020). The focus of the research team was on choosing individuals with broad knowledge and skill who could contribute meaningfully and with insightful observations to the study's goals.

During the selection process, efforts were made to ensure maximum variation and diversity among the participants. This involved considering factors such as professional background, years of experience, geographic location, and involvement in projects with varying levels of embodied carbon reduction initiatives. By including participants with diverse perspectives, the study aimed to capture a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the influence of quantity surveyors on embodied carbon reduction in construction projects within the UK context.

3.5 Ethical Consideration

Any research study must prioritise ethical issues, and this one examining the impact of quantity surveyors on the reduction of embodied carbon in UK building projects is no different. In order to respect participant rights, maintain participant confidentiality, and maintain the integrity of the

entire research process, the researcher is guided by ethical issues when carrying out the study. Getting participant's informed permission is a key ethical consideration. The study's objectives, methods, potential risks and benefits, confidentiality safeguards, and participant's freedom to leave at any time without penalty were all fully explained to them before the start of the interviews. Each participant provided their informed permission to ensure they were completely aware of their engagement and voluntarily consented to participate.

Throughout the whole study, anonymity and confidentiality were maintained. The identity of the participants and any private information disclosed during the interviews were carefully kept private. Each participant received a special identification code, and the study team alone had access to all of the data that were collected and securely stored. To protect the participants' privacy, all identifying information was eliminated or made anonymous during the analysis and reporting phase. The preservation of the health of participants is another ethical factor. The research team was aware that talking about issues like embodied carbon and sustainability can have an emotional or psychological effect on the participants. During the interviews, tact was used, and participants had the chance to express their ideas and experiences in a welcoming and nonjudgmental setting. Participants have access to sufficient debriefing and support systems should they need any help or additional details.

The study also complied with ethical standards by refraining from using any kind of coercion or manipulation. At any time, without penalty or pressure, participants were allowed to decline to take part in the study or to leave it altogether. All along the research process, the researchers made sure that the participants' autonomy and voluntary participation were respected. The researcher also followed ethical standards while reporting and sharing the results. To preserve confidentiality, the quotes and data from the participants were presented in an aggregated, de-identified format. Without misleading or distorting the opinions or experiences of the participants, the research findings were presented in an accurate and transparent manner. To maintain intellectual integrity and prevent plagiarism, proper acknowledgement and citation of prior research as well as contributions from other scholars were also ensured. It is important to note that ethical issues are continually taken into account during the research endeavour. Any ethical difficulties or concerns that surfaced during the research procedure were monitored and addressed by the research team. To make sure that ethical principles and norms were being followed, frequent ethical reflections and conversations were undertaken.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 Data Analysis and Findings

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents a summary of the data analysis performed on the thirty-one (31) respondents who participated in the study's questionnaire and interview. The purpose of the study is to assess the contribution and efficiency of quantity surveyors in lowering embodied carbon in UK construction projects. Identifying the potential influence of quantity surveyor's role in influencing embodied carbon on projects at various RIBA stages and evaluating the current practice of QS in influencing embodied carbon on projects are additional goals. These include defining the drive towards Net-Zero and the current standards and legislation that drive and inform it.

The researcher describes the strategy in this section, showing the results whenever possible with charts. On the provided data, concurrent inferential and descriptive statistical analyses are performed. The graphs and charts were made with Excel 2013 and SPSS 22.

Closed-ended questions were asked of respondents in the online survey to elicit pertinent responses, which were then presented in tables and graphs by the quantitative approach described in chapter three of the current study. With this approach, the research instrument's dependability will be increased and the examined themes will be better understood. In accordance with the rules provided, participant comments are utilized in this section without revealing any identifying information.

4.2 Response Rate

The cohort of the study consisted of 31, as previously mentioned. After data was acquired utilizing a Google form and an interviewing technique, 31 responses were noted. When considering the sample size, prior research (Meterko et al., 2015) have shown that a response rate of (100%) is considered to be a legitimately acceptable reply rate for an online survey.

But it's crucial to remember that a high response rate does not always translate into high-quality data. Important factors, such as the degree of sample representation, the effectiveness of the questionnaire structure, the clarity of the questions, and the accuracy of the methods used to collect

and analyze the data, were examined and discussed in relation to how they might affect the validity and reliability of the responses to the survey.

4.3 Respondents' Demographic Information

This section uses charts to emphasize the respondents' demographic data; however, the information was obtained from a UK construction project.

4.3.1 Gender

The chart below depicts the gender distribution of respondents, which reveals that more males participated in the survey than females. (80%) of the people who responded are males, and (20%) are females.

Figure 4.1: Characteristics of respondents by gender

4.3.2 Age group

The age groups of the respondents are depicted in the bar chart below. There are five categories of age specified in the survey and respondents have acted accordingly. From the results, (55%) of the

respondents are between 36-45 years of age, (22%) are between 18-35 years old, (14%) are 46-60 years, and (9%) are between 60 and above.

Figure 4.2: Age group of respondents

4.3.3 Job Position

In this study, the respondents' employment status was taken into account. As a consequence of the survey, it was discovered that (28%) of respondents were Chartered Quantity Surveyors, (24%) were, (18%) were Associate Directors, (17%) were Assistant/Graduate Quantity Surveyors, and (13%) were Directors.

Figure 4.3: Job positions of respondents

4.3.4 Working Experience

This research also takes into account the workers' most recent years of employment. According to the findings, most respondents (40%) had between zero to five years of job experience, (34%) had between eleven to twenty years of working experience, (22%) have six to ten years of working experience and (4%) of the respondents have above twenty years working experience.

Figure 4.4: Work experience of the respondents

4.3.5 Organisation Size

The results showed that when the respondents' organization types were taken into consideration, (43%) of them worked for medium-sized companies with employee sizes between 50 and 249, (36%) for small companies with employee sizes between one and forty-nine, and (21%) for large companies with employee sizes of 250 and more.

Figure 4.5: Organization size of respondents

4.4 Concept of Net-Zero

The results showed that (60%) of respondents were only somewhat familiar with the idea of Net-Zero and the current standards and legislation driving it in the construction industry, while (40%) of respondents were extremely familiar with these topics.

Figure 4.6: Familiarity level of respondents with the concept of Net-Zero

The results also showed that (45%) of respondents agreed that quantity surveyors can have an impact on the management of embodied carbon in construction projects at various stages of the RIBA (Royal Institute of British Architects), (26%) of respondents agreed that they can have a moderate impact, (18%) of respondents thought their impact could be limited, and (11%) of respondents agreed that the role of quantity surveyors can have no impact.

Additionally, according to (38%) of the respondents, effective waste management is a strategy quantity surveyors may use to help lower embodied carbon during a project's design and construction phases. However, (26%) of the respondents considered supply chain assessment and management as the best strategy, (18%) of the participants believe that energy-efficient design was the best strategy. (13%) of the respondents considered material substitution and optimization as the best strategy quantity surveyors can implement to contribute to the reduction of embodied carbon during the design and construction phases of a project.

The majority of the respondents (57%) were not aware of any specific tools, guidelines, or best practices that quantity surveyors can utilize to evaluate and address embodied carbon in construction projects while 43% of the respondents were aware of any specific tools, guidelines, or best practices that quantity surveyors can utilize to evaluate and address embodied carbon in

construction projects. The disparity in awareness levels of quantity surveyors provides a potential opportunity to increase knowledge among quantity surveyors about the techniques and methods that can be used to address embodied carbon.

The respondents (29%) majorly find the design team incorporating QS input on embodied carbon Projects very receptive, (27%) of the respondents considered them somewhat receptive, (23%) of the respondents were neutral, (14%) of the respondents considered them somewhat resistant and (7%) of the respondents considered them to be very resistant.

Figure 4.7: Respondents perspective on the involvement of Quantity Surveyors on embodied carbon project

In addition, (40%) of the respondents considered their involvement in embodied carbon project to play a crucial role in influencing the project outcome to a high extent, (35%) of the respondents considered their involvement to be to a very high extent, (13%) of the respondents considered their involvement to be at a low extent and (12%) of the respondents considered their involvement to be on a very low extent.

4.5 DISCUSSION

4.5.1 Based on Demographic

According to the findings, a sizable majority (80%) of the study's participants identified as men. This implies that the field of quantity surveying in the United Kingdom is predominantly occupied by males. The majority (55%) of the respondents are between the 36-45 age range, which implies that a substantial representation of the respondents between the ages 36-45 are people of mid-career professionals and individuals who likely possess substantial experience in the construction industry.

Also, (24%) were Chartered Quantity Surveyors, which implies the significant representation of Chartered Quantity Surveyors in the sample of respondents indicates that their specialised knowledge and responsibilities in building projects play a vital role in addressing the mitigation of embodied carbon.

The majority (40%) have 0-5 years of working experience. This implies that the upcoming generation of quantity surveyors may offer a fresh perspective on sustainability and carbon reduction in the sector. With a large proportion of the workforce in their early stages, there's potential for innovative approaches to tackle embodied carbon in building projects. Less-experienced quantity surveyors may be more receptive to sustainable practices due to their increased awareness of environmental issues. This suggests a potential for innovative solutions in the construction industry.

A greater part of the respondents (43%) worked in Medium-sized companies with a substantial labour force can successfully execute sustainability endeavours, hence exerting a significant impact on the incorporation of sustainable methodologies in building undertakings spanning the whole spectrum from initial design to procurement processes.

The majority (38%) responded to be somewhat familiar with Net- Zero which implies that this level of familiarity suggests that there exists a foundational knowledge base among respondents regarding Net-Zero principles and the pertinent regulations. Furthermore, the survey revealed that (45%) of respondents believe quantity surveyors can significantly reduce embodied carbon in construction projects, indicating their importance in sustainability efforts. (38%) believe efficient

waste management is a strategy that quantity surveyors can implement to contribute to embodied carbon reduction during the design and construction phases.

However, (57%) of respondents are unaware of specific tools, guidelines, or best practices that quantity surveyors can use to evaluate and address embodied carbon, indicating a need for increased awareness and education in the industry. Additionally, (29%) of respondents perceive the design team as receptive to incorporating quantity surveyors' input on embodied carbon projects, suggesting a positive collaborative atmosphere between quantity surveyors and the design team. This suggests that quantity surveyors can leverage this receptiveness to effectively influence decisions that impact embodied carbon reduction.

4.5.2 Perceived Impact of Quantity Surveyors

A notable proportion of the participants (45%) hold the belief that quantity surveyors exert a favourable influence on the management of embodied carbon in building endeavours. This implies that the individuals in question hold the belief that quantity surveyors have a major role to play in the reduction of carbon emissions during different phases of building endeavours. Approximately (26%) of the participants perceive quantity surveyors to possess a moderate level of influence in the management of embodied carbon. Although the positive group is considered stronger, it is important to recognise the contribution of the opposing group to carbon reduction efforts. A few of the participants (18%) see the influence of quantity surveyors to be constrained in their ability to effectively manage embodied carbon. This group is inclined to hold the belief that quantity surveyors do possess a certain degree of significance, but maybe not as substantial as other stakeholders. A small proportion of participants (11%) hold the viewpoint that quantity surveyors cannot influence the management of embodied carbon in construction projects. This approach posits a sense of scepticism regarding the efficacy of quantity surveyors in mitigating carbon emissions.

4.5.3 Strategies for Reducing Embodied Carbon

A significant proportion of the respondents (38%) acknowledge the importance of waste reduction in the construction industry. They believe that good waste management is a crucial method for quantity surveyors to contribute to the reduction of embodied carbon. Effective waste management practices indirectly reduce carbon emissions by minimising energy-intensive processes involved

in material manufacture and disposal activities. The growing utilisation of this approach indicates a growing recognition of the environmental impacts associated with construction waste.

The significance of addressing carbon reduction during the design process is shown by the (26%) of participants who perceive energy-efficient design as the most effective resolution. The data presented in this study highlight the significant influence that quantity surveyors exert on the overall energy efficiency of buildings. These strategies can effectively reduce the carbon footprint of a building, encompassing both its construction and operational phases.

Merely (13%) of participants saw material substitution and optimisation as significantly crucial methods. The selection of materials can exert a substantial influence on the reduction of embodied carbon through the deliberate choice of materials with diminished carbon footprints. The relatively smaller share, however, implies that there is scope for enhancing the dissemination of information on the carbon-reducing capabilities of specific construction materials.

The evaluation and management of carbon emissions across the whole supply chain of construction materials is of utmost importance. This suggests a level of understanding of the interconnectedness of various elements inside a structure. The collaboration between quantity surveyors and manufacturers and retailers is essential in advocating for the adoption of ecologically sustainable goods and practices across the whole supply chain. This will facilitate the integration of sustainable materials, products, and processes into construction projects. This can be achieved by setting sustainability goals with suppliers, highlighting the financial benefits of using sustainable materials and sharing best practices.

The allocation of varying weights to different solutions indicates the necessity of implementing a complete approach to effectively mitigate embodied carbon. The effectiveness and comprehensiveness of carbon emissions reduction methods may be increased by integrating waste management, energy-efficient design, material substitution, and supply chain optimization.

The level of knowledge and insight possessed by the respondents may be evidenced by their selection of tactics. This discovery underscores the need of offering ongoing education and training on sustainable practices and their impact on reducing embodied carbon to quantity surveyors as well as other professionals within the construction sector.

The findings suggest that fostering multidisciplinary collaboration within the construction industry is crucial to achieve considerable embodied carbon reductions. The effective adoption of various approaches throughout the building process necessitates collaboration among architects, engineers, quantity surveyors, contractors, and suppliers.

4.5.4 Awareness of Tools and Practices

When it comes to assessing and mitigating the impact of embodied carbon in construction projects, a significant proportion of participants (57%) lack knowledge of specific tools, standards, or recommended approaches that quantity surveyors may utilise. This implies that there could be a need for more training and promotion in this particular domain. Conversely, a majority of the respondents (43%) exhibit knowledge of specific resources, such as guidelines or best practices, that are accessible to professionals in the field of quantity surveying. This observation suggests that a significant number of individuals possess knowledge of the available resources and strategies for mitigating embodied carbon.

4.5.5 Receptiveness of Design Teams to QS Input

Almost one-third of respondents (29%) find design teams incorporating quantity surveyor input on embodied carbon projects to be very receptive, indicating a positive collaboration between quantity surveyors and design teams. A similar percentage (27%) see design teams as somewhat receptive to quantity surveyor input, suggesting a moderate level of cooperation. A significant minority (23%) of respondents have a neutral perspective on the receptiveness of design teams, indicating that they neither strongly resist nor enthusiastically embrace quantity surveyor involvement. About (14%) of the respondents find design teams somewhat resistant to quantity surveyor input, suggesting potential challenges in integrating carbon reduction strategies. A smaller portion (7%) of respondents perceive design teams to be very resistant to quantity surveyor input, which could imply significant barriers to collaboration.

In summary, the results highlight varying perceptions about the role of quantity surveyors in managing embodied carbon in construction projects. While a notable portion of respondents acknowledges the positive impact of quantity surveyors, there is also a range of opinions about their effectiveness and the strategies they can employ. The awareness of tools and practices and the receptiveness of design teams further emphasize the need for continued education,

collaboration, and innovation in the construction industry to address the carbon footprint of projects.

Thematic Analysis

The results from the structured interview is presented in specific themes highlighting key issues emerging from the interview.

4.5.6 Reduction of embodied carbon and consequential outcome

Theme 1: Optimizing material quality

Materials of high quality are characterised by their reduced susceptibility to rapid degradation or obsolescence, resulting in a decreased output of waste. This practise aids in the reduction of the environmental consequences of garbage disposal and the carbon emissions linked to waste management. This aligns with the research conducted by Victoria and Perera (2018), which supports the notion that quantity surveyors have the potential to mitigate embodied carbon emissions through educated decision-making about low-carbon materials and optimising material use.

4.5.7 Method to reduce embodied carbon

Theme 2: Carbon Auditing

Carbon auditing is widely used to reduce embodied carbon in projects. This technique involves meticulously monitoring and assessing a project's carbon emissions, from raw material extraction through waste disposal. Stakeholders can set targeted reduction goals by identifying "hotspots," or crucial places, that contribute significantly to carbon emissions throughout the project. Life cycle assessment (LCA) helps make informed material choices, improve processes, and upgrade technology to decrease carbon footprints (Rasmussen et al., 2020). Carbon auditing encourages low-carbon product selection, process efficiency, and supply chain partner engagement in emission reduction (Ali et al., 2020). This strategy promotes sustainability and reduces embodied carbon to mitigate climate change. This technique includes monitoring and reporting results and advocating for favourable legislation.

4.5.8 Barriers

Theme 3: Lack of awareness

There exists a potential scenario wherein several stakeholders, including client, designers, and contractors, may lack a comprehensive comprehension of the significance of embedded carbon and the benefits associated with carbon auditing procedures. The absence of comprehension in this regard may provide challenges for individuals in their efforts to engage in actions aimed at mitigating carbon emissions (Willhelm Abeydeera et al., 2019; Austin and Converse, 2021).

Theme 4: Cost implication

The implementation of carbon reduction initiatives may necessitate investments in innovative technology, materials, or process modifications. Achieving a harmonious equilibrium between the costs associated with low-budget initiatives and the potential long-term savings they might provide can be a challenge (Robati et al. 2021 and Recio-Saucedo et al., 2022).

Theme 5: Availability and quality of data

Gathering accurate data on carbon emissions across the whole lifecycle of a project might provide significant challenges. The presence of incomplete or inaccurate data might lead to judgements that lack reliability and hinder the identification of genuinely threatening locations (Chastas et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2020).

4.5.8 Strategy to overcome barriers

Theme 6: Education and training

By offering stakeholders training opportunities like workshops, seminars, and training programmes, it is feasible to raise their understanding of embodied carbon and the benefits of carbon auditing approaches. This is in line with Ohene et al. (2022) report which affirms that the promotion of dedication to transformation can be enhanced by increasing awareness regarding the environmental and economic advantages associated with reducing embodied carbon.

Theme 7: Collaborative and partnership

The adoption of decreasing embodied carbon may be enhanced by the promotion of collaboration within the sector, which includes the active involvement of designers, contractors, suppliers, and

other pertinent stakeholders. The exchange of knowledge, experiences, and recommendations about the most effective approaches has the potential to foster the creation of novel ideas and accelerate the implementation process (Choi et al., 2020).

Theme 8: Technology and data-driven tools

The advancement of software tools and technologies that prioritise ease of use for users can make the practice of carbon auditing more viable and accessible to a wider spectrum of persons. According to Olabi et al. (2022), the availability of these tools will enable stakeholders to quantify and evaluate embodied carbon, hence increasing the accessibility of this topic to a wider audience.

CHAPTER FIVE

Summary, Conclusions and Recommendation

5.0 Summary

This study critically appraise the influence of quantity surveyors on the reduction of embodied carbon in construction projects within the UK. The finding of the study reveals the demographics of the participants, focusing on gender, age group, job position, years of professional experience, and organisational size.

The implementation of several measures is crucial in mitigating embodied carbon, including but not limited to effective waste management, design practises that prioritise energy efficiency, replacement and optimisation of materials, and thorough investigation of the supply chain. The research further emphasises the necessity of ongoing education and the distribution of information within the respective profession.

The theme analysis underscores the importance of decision-making that is impacted by the economic advantages associated with carbon reduction methods. This study brings emphasis to the potential for both cost savings and environmental benefits. The quantification and management of carbon emissions during the course of a project are greatly aided by the carbon auditing process.

Conclusively, the study identifies several obstacles to the adoption of embedded carbon practices, including a lack of knowledge, financial concerns, and data problems. To overcome these obstacles and facilitate widespread acceptance, the study underscores the significance of educational initiatives and training programmes, joint integration efforts, and the utilisation of technology-driven solutions. By endorsing these proposals, stakeholders have the potential to facilitate the adoption of more extensive and efficient strategies for reducing embodied carbon in the construction sector. This would not only contribute to environmental sustainability but also accord with international climate objectives.

5.1 Conclusion

This study provides valuable insights into multiple facets of the endeavour to reduce embodied carbon in construction projects within the UK. By examining various aspects of this issue, the research contributes to a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with minimising the carbon footprint of construction activities within the UK. Through a

comprehensive analysis, the study illuminates key considerations, strategies, and potential solutions for effectively addressing embodied carbon in the construction industry within the UK. The research intends to inform and direct stakeholders in their efforts to promote sustainable practices and minimise the environmental impact of building projects in the UK by throwing light on these crucial factors. It also emphasises the central role of carbon auditing as an approach to assessing and quantifying the carbon emissions associated with various activities or processes.

By integrating economic factors and carbon auditing, decision-makers can effectively evaluate the environmental impact of their choices and prioritise options that offer both economic advantages and reduced carbon footprints. Furthermore, it is important to highlight the various obstacles that stakeholders may encounter when attempting to adopt carbon reduction methods. One significant barrier is the lack of awareness among these individuals or organisations regarding the importance and potential benefits of implementing such strategies. This lack of knowledge can hinder their willingness to engage in carbon reduction efforts. Additionally, stakeholders may face challenges related to data availability and accuracy.

In order to effectively reduce carbon emissions, it is crucial to have access to reliable and comprehensive data on current emission levels and sources. However, gathering and analysing this data can be a complex and time-consuming task. Moreover, the accuracy of the collected data is paramount, as any discrepancies or errors can undermine the effectiveness of carbon reduction initiatives. Therefore, it is essential to address these obstacles and give interested parties the knowledge and tools they need to do so. By raising awareness about the significance of carbon reduction and providing support in data collection and analysis, stakeholders can be better equipped to adopt in order to surmount the obstacles identified, the study posits a range of effective strategies.

One such strategy is education, which involves imparting knowledge and skills to individuals in order to enhance their understanding and ability to navigate barriers. By equipping individuals with the necessary information and tools, education can empower them to overcome the challenges they face. Collaboration is another key strategy highlighted in the study. By fostering partnerships and cooperation among various stakeholders, collaboration can facilitate the pooling of resources, expertise, and perspectives. This collective effort can lead to the development of innovative solutions and the sharing of the findings of this study underscores the imperative for heightened

consciousness, enhanced cooperation across various industries, and the development of cutting-edge methodologies to adequately tackle the issue of embodied carbon.

There is a pressing demand for a comprehensive understanding of the environmental impact associated with the production and use of materials in various sectors. This necessitates the cultivation of a collective consciousness among stakeholders, including policymakers, industry leaders, and researchers, to recognise the significance of embodied carbon and its implications for sustainable development.

Furthermore, the findings highlight the importance of fostering collaboration among different industries. Given that embodied carbon is a multifaceted challenge that transcends sectoral boundaries, it is crucial to establish partnerships and foster knowledge exchange between diverse industries. This can facilitate the sharing of best practices, expertise, and resources, ultimately leading to more effective strategies to overcome the barriers within the UK.

5.2 Recommendation

Based on the comprehensive analysis and empirical evidence derived from the research, a prudent and well-informed recommendation has been formulated to address the identified issues and optimise the desired outcomes.

Promote Industry-wide Collaboration: The complex and multifaceted structure of the construction sector, characterised by a diverse range of stakeholders, requires a coordinated approach in order to effectively tackle the difficulties associated with embodied carbon. It is imperative for professionals in the fields of architecture, engineering, quantity surveying, and contracting to collaborate and exchange knowledge, insights, and best practices. The establishment of cross-functional teams or forums, in which experts may collaboratively engage in brainstorming, strategizing, and implementing efforts aimed at reducing carbon emissions, has the potential to provide more comprehensive and significant solutions.

Education and Training: Implement comprehensive educational initiatives aimed at enhancing individuals' understanding and awareness of strategies for mitigating embodied carbon emissions. These projects must prioritise engagement with stakeholders across many levels, including industry experts, decision-makers, and investors. Workshops, webinars, and training courses may be designed with a focus on highlighting the environmental and economic benefits associated with

reducing embodied carbon. Additionally, these educational programmes can provide practical guidance on effectively implementing such strategies. One approach to achieve this objective is placing greater focus on the advantages associated with reducing embodied carbon.

Technology advancement: The proposed approach involves allocating resources towards the development and dissemination of technology-based solutions and software tools that prioritise user-friendliness. The primary objective is to enhance the accessibility of carbon audits and data analysis processes. These technologies can simplify the measurement, monitoring, and management of embedded carbon emissions, hence expanding the accessibility of these tools to a wider range of specialists.

Research and Development: The promotion of research and development in the field of reducing embodied carbon is of utmost significance, with a specific focus on the generation of novel materials, technologies, and methodologies. The building and construction business has the potential to achieve more ambitious carbon reduction targets through promoting innovation, hence facilitating continuous improvement of industrial practices.

Establishing industry standards and guidelines: The creation of established standards and best practices that are specific to embodied carbon can help stakeholders by giving them a clear road map. Ensuring adherence to these guidelines is essential in order to maintain consistency in the implementation of strategies, regardless of the size or diversity of the projects. Industry groups can proactively establish these standards in collaboration with subject matter experts, so assuring their broad dissemination and effective implementation.

Recognizing and rewarding best practices: The implementation of recognition programmes that highlight and acknowledge successful projects and teams in the reduction of embodied carbon would be advantageous. These schemes would fulfil the objective of incentivizing professionals and enterprises. Promote a culture of competitiveness aimed at fostering sustainability within the industry through the dissemination of success stories and the acknowledgement of exemplary practices. This will incentivize a greater number of stakeholders to embrace practices that are comparable to those that have been noticed and acknowledged.

Campaigns for Awareness and Advocacy: There is an urgent need to enhance understanding regarding the need of reducing embodied carbon, achieved via the deployment of targeted

awareness initiatives. These initiatives can foster a broader understanding and desire for ecologically conscientious construction practises through engaging with key stakeholders, industry associations, and the wider public. In addition, stakeholders should engage in advocacy efforts aimed at influencing government policies and regulations that support and incentivize initiatives focused on reducing embodied carbon. Such actions would foster an environment that encourages the broad implementation of these projects.

5.3 Limitation to the Study

This study offers valuable insights into the implementation of practices aimed at reducing embodied carbon and the viewpoints of stakeholders within UK construction companies. But there are a lot of restrictions to take into account. There is a chance that the sample, which was drawn solely from one particular construction project in the United Kingdom, was too narrowly focused to adequately represent the variety of viewpoints present in the worldwide construction industry.

Hence, it is plausible that the outcomes may not exhibit universal applicability, especially when considering larger corporations, diverse geographical settings, or unique regulatory frameworks. Focusing only on the construction projects within the United Kingdom may provide challenges when attempting to extrapolate the research findings to other regions characterised by distinct economic and social dynamics. Furthermore, the validity of the research is contingent upon the use of self-reported data, so introducing the potential for self-reporting bias and potentially compromising the accuracy of the findings.

A comprehensive understanding of the evolving practises aimed at reducing embodied carbon can be obtained by longitudinal research conducted over an extended duration. Furthermore, the research has a significant focus on carbon auditing and utilises a restricted range of methodologies, potentially disregarding innovative techniques, technologies, or practices in the procedure. It is conceivable that the research methodology, mostly centred on interviews and questionnaires, may not effectively capture the intricacies of practices as compared to direct observation or in-depth case studies.

Furthermore, this study does not provide a direct quantification of the impact that these practices have on the observable reduction of carbon emissions. It is acknowledged how important collaboration is, yet the role and impact of quantity surveyors are the main focus of this study. This

implies that the comprehensive viewpoints of architects, engineers, contractors, and policymakers are not duly considered. In conclusion, it is plausible that the aforementioned results may not fully include several confounding factors, such as the prevailing economic conditions and advancements in technology.

These limitations highlight the possibility for future research that might expand the scope, enhance the methodology, and provide a more comprehensive knowledge of practices aimed at reducing embodied carbon in the construction sector.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1: Questionnaire

A CRITICAL APPRAISAL OF THE INFLUENCE OF QUANTITY SURVEYORS ON THE REDUCTION OF EMBODIED CARBON IN CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS WITHIN THE UK.

Dear Respondent,

I appreciate your willingness to participate in my research study on the current practice of Quantity Surveyors in influencing embodied carbon on projects. The objective of this study is to gain insights into the role of Quantity Surveyors in addressing embodied carbon and to assess the current practices in the industry. Your participation will greatly contribute to the understanding of this research study.

Please be rest assured that your responses will be kept confidential and will be solely used for academic research purposes.

Thank you for your participation and valuable contribution to this study.

Husseini Musa
Researcher

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

1. What is your gender?

- (a) Male
- (b) Female

2. What is your Age?

- (a) 18-35 years
- (b) 36-45 years
- (c) 46-60 years
- (d) Above 60 years

3. What is your position in the organisation?

- (a) Assistant/ Graduate quantity surveyor
- (b) Chartered Quantity Surveyor
- (c) Senior quantity surveyor
- (d) Associate Director/ Partner
- (e) Director/ Partner

4. Please indicate your years of experience in the UK construction industry.

- (a) 0 - 5 years
- (b) 6 -10 years
- (c) 11-20 years
- (d) Above 20 years

5. What is the size of your organization

- (a) Small (1 to 49 employees)
- (b) Medium (50 to 249 employees)
- (c) Large (250 employees and above)

SECTION B

6. How familiar are you with the concept of Net-Zero and the current standards and legislation driving it in the construction industry?

- (a) Very familiar
- (b) Somewhat familiar
- (c) Not familiar

7. In your experience, how do you think the role of quantity surveyors can impact the management of embodied carbon in construction projects at different stages of the RIBA (Royal Institute of British Architects) framework?

- (a) Significant impact
- (b) Moderate impact
- (c) Limited impact
- (d) No impact

8. How receptive do you find design team incorporating QS input on embodied carbon Project?

- (a) Very receptive
- (b) Somewhat receptive
- (c) Neutral
- (d) Somewhat resistant
- (e) Very resistant

9. Do you believe enough is being done by the client and design team to enable active involvement of the QS towards reducing carbon emissions in projects?

(a) Yes

(b) No

10. In reference to Q11, please briefly explain the reason behind your answer?

11. To what extent did your involvement on embodied carbon project play a crucial role in influencing the project outcome?

(a) Very high extent

(b) High extent

(c) Low extent

(d) Very low extent

12. Are you aware of any specific tools, guidelines, or best practices that quantity surveyors can utilize to evaluate and address embodied carbon in construction projects?

(a) Yes, please specify _____

(b) No

13. If Yes to Q12, please specify the tools quantity surveyors can adopt? _____

14. What measures or strategies do you believe quantity surveyors can implement to contribute to the reduction of embodied carbon during the design and construction phases of a project? _____

15. In what ways do you think your role in embodied carbon projects will impact overall project outcome?

16. What strategy do you recommend that Quantity Surveyors incorporate in an effort to increase their influence on projects aimed at mitigating embodied carbon? _____

Appendix 2: Interview Response

A CRITICAL APPRAISAL OF THE INFLUENCE OF QUANTITY SURVEYORS ON THE REDUCTION OF EMBODIED CARBON IN CONSTRUCTION PROJECTS WITHIN THE UK.

Interview 1

1. Can you share instances of specific projects where you successfully influenced the reduction of embodied carbon and what was the consequential outcome?

- While working on a retail development project, I was part of the commercial team that conducted a comprehensive life cycle costing of the project. This LCA costing allowed the commercial team to make informed decisions that had both environmental and financial impacts. By optimizing material use, enhancing energy efficiency, reducing waste, and extending product life, we were able to identify potential cost savings and contribute to the project's overall sustainability goals. This approach not only showcased our commitment to environmentally-conscious practices but also demonstrated the practical advantages of considering the full life cycle of a project. It's a great illustration of how LCA costing can drive effective decision-making, aligning with long-term financial benefits and sustainable choices.

2. Can you describe any of the methods/initiatives that you adopted to exert influence on the reduction of embodied carbon in projects?

- The incorporation of Life Cycle Assessments for materials and building systems is one of the methods and initiatives that was adopted on the project. This method evaluates the environmental impact of materials and processes throughout the lifecycle of the building. This is usually done by analyzing factors such as raw material extraction, transportation, manufacturing, construction, and end-of-life disposal, project teams can identify high-impact areas and make informed decisions to reduce embodied carbon.

3. What were the most significant barriers that you faced when adopting these methods/initiatives on the embodied carbon projects which you were involved?

- Availability and Quality of data related to embodied carbon was a challenge. In order to effectively manage and reduce embodied carbon, having accurate and comprehensive data is essential. Insufficient data, particularly concerning supply chain information and material life cycle assessments, can impede the ability to make informed decisions and accurately assess the environmental impact of a project.

4. What strategies do you think QS can adopt to overcome these barriers and increase its influence in the adoption of embodied carbon practices in projects?

Leveraging technology and data-driven tools to manage and analyze data is a powerful approach that can significantly enhance the role of Quantity Surveyors in quantifying and managing embodied carbon impacts. By integrating life cycle assessment (LCA) data into cost estimating processes, Quantity Surveyors can contribute to informed decision-making and more sustainable project outcomes.

Interview 2

1. Can you share instances of specific projects where you successfully influenced the reduction of embodied carbon and what was the consequential outcome?

- In a commercial building project, I collaborated closely with the design team to specify low-carbon concrete alternatives and lightweight construction materials. By opting for low-carbon concrete alternatives and lightweight materials, we successfully achieved a remarkable 15% reduction in embodied carbon. This reduction not only aligns with the project's sustainability goals but also demonstrates a commitment to environmental responsibility and resource efficiency. These savings in material costs contributed to overall project budget optimization, potentially freeing up resources for other important aspects of the project. In addition, collaborative efforts and decision-making demonstrate the positive synergy between sustainable design choices and financial outcomes. The ability to balance both environmental and economic considerations highlights my expertise in effectively managing and influencing projects to achieve multiple objectives.

2. Can you describe any of the methods/initiatives that you adopted to exert influence on the reduction of embodied carbon in projects?

- In the course of my experience on embodied carbon projects, the implementation of material test fits has emerged as a strategic methodology. The specifications of construction materials play an important role in influencing the project cost. This is achieved through analysis of the cost implication of opting for low-carbon or carbon-neutral materials and considering alternative materials with lower embodied carbon. The potential outcome of this analysis could be an addition or decrease to the budgeted project cost.

3. What were the most significant barriers that you faced when adopting these methods/initiatives on the embodied carbon projects which you were involved?

- One of the primary challenges encountered was a lack of awareness and understanding of embodied carbon and its implications among project stakeholders was a major challenge. This knowledge gap hindered effective communication and decision-making throughout the project lifecycle.

4. What strategies do you think QS can adopt to overcome these barriers and increase its influence in the adoption of embodied carbon practices in projects?

- One effective approach, among others, that Quantity Surveyors (QS) can employ to surmount barriers and augment their influence is the strategic utilization of Collaborative Integration. This strategy entails fostering interdisciplinary collaboration through regular meetings and workshops with architects, engineers, and other stakeholders early in the design phase will collectively address project sustainability challenges. By participating in interdisciplinary discussions at the project's initial stages, Quantity Surveyors can influence material and design decisions that align with project objectives and most importantly cost.

Interview 3

1. Can you share instances of specific projects where you successfully influenced the reduction of embodied carbon and what was the consequential outcome?

- On an industrial facility expansion, I advocated for the reuse of existing infrastructure and equipment wherever feasible. By minimizing the need for new materials and construction, we achieved a 15% reduction in embodied carbon and ensured a seamless integration of old and new elements.

2. Can you describe any of the methods/initiatives that you adopted to exert influence on the reduction of embodied carbon in projects?

- I would say that the concept of Value Engineering because it involves the comprehensive assessment of the materials and systems to optimize performance and durability. The ultimate goal is reducing the need for replacements and minimizing overall embodied carbon.

3. What were the most significant barriers that you faced when adopting these methods/initiatives on the embodied carbon projects which you were involved?

- Technological and Methodological Complexity were some of the challenges encountered on the project. This is as a result of some methods and tools for assessing and reducing embodied carbon being perceived as complex and resource-intensive, deterring their widespread adoption. A lack of standardized methodologies further complicated implementation.

4. What strategies do you think QS can adopt to overcome these barriers and increase its influence in the adoption of embodied carbon practices in projects?

- Stakeholder engagement emerges as a pivotal avenue for Quantity Surveyors to proactively connect with clients, contractors, and regulatory entities, advocating for the meaningful integration of QS expertise in embodied carbon projects. It is perceived that the design team have a significant

influence over embodied carbon reduction measures. Through open and transparent communication on both the environmental and economic implications, Quantity Surveyors can assert their role in influencing decision-making processes and contribute substantively to the broader spectrum of embodied carbon reduction practices.

Interview 4

1. Can you share instances of specific projects where you successfully influenced the reduction of embodied carbon and what was the consequential outcome?

- During a mixed-use project, I engaged in a collaborative partnership with suppliers to procure locally-sourced materials, thereby effectively curtailing transportation-related emissions. This meticulous strategy culminated in a commendable 10% reduction in embodied carbon, simultaneously fostering a symbiotic relationship with the local economy. This conscientious approach tangibly elevated the project's sustainability stature and contributed to its holistic environmental objectives.

2. Can you describe any of the methods/initiatives that you adopted to exert influence on the reduction of embodied carbon in projects?

- One of the strategies utilized to affect the embedded project outcomes is cost-benefit analysis. This method involves the evaluation of innovative materials and technologies factoring in the long-term carbon impacts in conjunction with initial project cost. This approach ensures a comprehensive evaluation of sustainable solutions that harmonize environmental considerations with economic viability.

3. What were the most significant barriers that you faced when adopting these methods/initiatives on the embodied carbon projects which you were involved?

- The issue of cost implications emerged as a significant concern. The perceived higher costs associated with adopting low-carbon materials and technologies sometimes clashed with budget constraints, affecting project feasibility. In my experience, QS professionals often operate within tightly controlled budgets. The integration of embodied carbon considerations oftentimes leads to increased costs, potentially conflicting with clients' immediate financial objectives.
- In addition, despite the push for sustainability, some project stakeholders, including clients and contractors, may prioritize conventional practices over embodied carbon considerations. This Stakeholder resistance can limit the influence of QS professionals.

4. What strategies do you think QS can adopt to overcome these barriers and increase its influence in the adoption of embodied carbon practices in projects?

- Integrating embodied carbon considerations into life cycle costing assessments can enable Quantity Surveyors to highlight the long-term benefits of low-carbon strategies. In addition to that, Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration between Quantity Surveyors and the design team comprising of architects, engineers, sustainability experts, and other stakeholders. This cross-disciplinary approach fosters a holistic understanding of embodied carbon and facilitates integration into project decisions.

Interview 5

1. Can you share instances of specific projects where you successfully influenced the reduction of embodied carbon and what was the consequential outcome?

- As part of an educational development, I championed the implementation of Sterling cost software to optimize material quantities and reduce construction waste. This approach could have resulted in a 20% reduction in embodied carbon and allowed for efficient project management. However, the project was suspended due to planning permits concerns.

2. Can you describe any of the methods/initiatives that you adopted to exert influence on the reduction of embodied carbon in projects?

- Carbon Auditing entails a thorough process of accurately quantifying or estimating carbon emissions in accordance with environmental targets. It is important for QS on embodied carbon project to have an understanding of carbon auditing. Some initiatives involve calculating the embodied carbon of a project and then offsetting these emissions through various means, such as investing in renewable energy projects or reforestation efforts.

3. What were the most significant barriers that you faced when adopting these methods/initiatives on the embodied carbon projects which you were involved?

- A prevailing challenge is the limited Decision-Making Authority of a quantity surveyor. While QS professionals provide valuable input, they may lack the final decision-making authority in selecting materials and construction methods. The ultimate choices often lie with architects, engineers, and project managers, limiting QS influence.
- A notable challenge arises from the inherent conflict between short-term cost-saving objectives and the more expansive realm of long-term sustainability goals. Quantity Surveying professionals often find themselves navigating between immediate financial considerations with the broader environmental agenda.

4. What strategies do you think QS can adopt to overcome these barriers and increase its influence in the adoption of embodied carbon practices in projects?

- Equipping Quantity Surveyors with the right Education and Training will provide a comprehensive understanding of embodied carbon concepts, measurement methodologies, and sustainable materials is essential. Only a few quantity surveyors in the United Kingdom are involved in projects with embodied carbon requirements and many more need to expand their knowledge on this concept to empower them to confidently engage with project teams and stakeholders on carbon reduction strategies.

Interview 6

1. Can you share instances of specific projects where you successfully influenced the reduction of embodied carbon and what was the consequential outcome?

- During a facility expansion, I proposed the use of prefabricated modular construction techniques. This decision not only streamlined construction and reduced waste but also resulted in an increase in the projected estimated cost. While the choice led to operational efficiencies and reduced environmental impact, it is essential to acknowledge the financial implications that arose in the pursuit of these broader project objectives.

2. Can you describe any of the methods/initiatives that you adopted to exert influence on the reduction of embodied carbon in projects?

- Advising project stakeholders regarding innovative construction methods such as Prefabrication and modular Construction can significantly reduce onsite construction waste and material usage. These approaches streamline construction processes and often require fewer materials overall, contributing to lower embodied carbon and better project performance.

3. What were the most significant barriers that you faced when adopting these methods/initiatives on the embodied carbon projects which you were involved?

- The intricate nature of quantifying embodied carbon across diverse materials and processes introduces a layer of complexity that demands specialized expertise. Quantity surveyors might find it challenging to navigate the technical complexities of accurate assessment.
- The global nature of supply chains posed challenges in sourcing low-carbon materials, especially in regions with limited availability of sustainable options.

4. What strategies do you think QS can adopt to overcome these barriers and increase its influence in the adoption of embodied carbon practices in projects?

- Fostering enhanced Communication skills equips Quantity Surveyors to effectively convey the implications of embodied carbon to diverse audiences, including clients and stakeholders. Clear communication fosters understanding and support for sustainable choices.